

SECTION 7.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT & ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY: SCIENTIFIC STRATEGIES FOR PRESERVING THE PLANET

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DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING NUCLEAR ENERGY IN UKRAINE IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND ENERGY SECURITY

Abstract. *It is essential to create conditions for the sustainable development of the national economy by ensuring access to reliable, resilient, and modern*

energy sources. This strategy envisages bringing the energy sector of our state as close as possible to climate neutrality. Climate neutrality of Ukraine implies the full functioning of national energy markets and their integration into international markets. It also includes the development of an innovative energy system, its decentralization, the production of clean energy, and overcoming the current problem of energy poverty.

To implement the key principles of Ukraine's Energy Strategy in terms of economic feasibility, environmental friendliness, and accessibility, it is necessary to take into account the fact that nuclear energy has its own advantages and disadvantages. Among these disadvantages is that, although nuclear power generation requires a relatively small amount of fuel, nuclear power plants produce a significant amount of waste. This raises the issue of its disposal in a way that does not harm the environment or future generations. This determines the relevance of developing methods for the processing and disposal of radioactive waste generated by nuclear power plants.

Keywords: climate neutrality, development of an innovative energy system, nuclear energy, disposal of radioactive waste.

Introduction. According to estimates by the International Energy Agency, global energy consumption has increased by more than 3 % annually over the past 30 years.

In accordance with the Energy Strategy of Ukraine until 2050, it is important to create conditions for the sustainable development of the national economy by ensuring access to reliable, resilient, and modern energy sources. This strategy envisages bringing the energy sector of our state as close as possible to climate neutrality over the next 25 years [1].

Climate neutrality of Ukraine implies the full functioning of national energy markets and their integration into international markets. It also includes the development of an innovative energy system, its decentralization, the production of clean energy, and overcoming the current problem of energy poverty [2].

Ensuring the state energy sector with its own resources, taking into account economic feasibility, can be achieved through the development of alternative energy sources. Nuclear energy belongs to such sources. It produces a huge amount of energy based on a relatively small amount of fuel.

The growth of the world's population, the depletion of fossil fuel reserves, the increasing impact of the greenhouse effect, and the lack of alternative sources with the required energy capacity contribute to the increasing role of nuclear energy in the energy supply of the global economy. Currently, more than 440 nuclear power units are operating and 25 more are under construction in 30 countries around the world. The capacity of nuclear energy sources may double by 2020 and quadruple by 2050. In a number of countries, nuclear energy occupies a dominant position, producing more than half of the required electricity. Ukraine is among these countries.

To implement the key principles of Ukraine's Energy Strategy in terms of economic feasibility, environmental friendliness, and accessibility, it should be noted that the use of nuclear energy has its own advantages and disadvantages. Among these disadvantages is the fact that, although nuclear power generation requires a relatively small amount of fuel, nuclear power plants produce a large amount of waste. This raises the issue of its disposal in order to avoid harm to the environment and future generations. This determines the current relevance of developing methods for the processing and disposal of radioactive waste from nuclear power plants.

Article Purpose. There is a need to study nuclear energy as a component of achieving sustainable development goals and its role in the energy security of Ukraine under conditions of achieving climate neutrality. In order to implement the key principles of Ukraine's Energy Strategy in terms of economic feasibility, environmental sustainability, and accessibility, there is a need to substantiate the improvement of methods for the processing and disposal of radioactive waste from nuclear power plants in order to minimize their harmful impact on the environment and future generations.

Results. Ukraine ranks among the top eight countries in the world in terms of electricity generation at nuclear power plants and among the top five countries in terms of the share of nuclear-generated electricity in the total volume of electricity production [3]. Table 1 presents the percentage of electricity generated by nuclear power plants in the total electricity production in different countries around the world for the period from 2015 to 2024 [4]. Nuclear energy in Ukraine is an important component of the overall fuel and energy complex and occupies a leading position in the country's electricity supply [5].

Table 1

**Electricity generation at nuclear power plants
in different countries (as a percentage of total
electricity production)**

Country or area	Nuclear share of electricity (%)										Nuclear electricity production (billion kWh)	
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2023	2024
Argentina	4.8	5.6	4.5	4.7	5.9	7.5	7.2	5.4	6.3	7.4	9.0	10.4
Belgium	37.5	51.7	49.9	39.0	47.6	39.1	50.8	46.4	41.2	40.5	31.3	29.7
Brazil	2.8	2.9	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.1	2.4	2.5	2.2	2.3	13.7	14.9
Bulgaria	31.3	35.0	34.3	34.7	37.5	40.8	34.6	32.6	40.4	41.6	15.5	15.1
Canada	16.6	15.6	14.6	14.9	14.9	14.6	14.3	12.9	13.7	13.4	83.5	81.2
Czech Rep	32.5	29.4	33.1	34.5	35.2	37.3	36.6	36.7	40.0	40.2	28.7	28.0
Finland	33.7	33.7	33.2	32.4	34.7	33.9	32.8	35.0	42.0	39.1	32.8	31.1
France	76.3	72.3	71.6	71.7	70.6	70.6	69.0	62.5	64.8	67.3	323.8	364.4
Germany	14.1	13.1	11.6	11.7	12.4	11.3	11.9	5.8	1.4	0	6.7	0
Hungary	52.7	51.3	50.0	50.6	49.2	48.0	46.8	47.0	48.8	47.1	15.1	15.2
Japan	0.5	2.2	3.6	6.2	7.5	5.1	7.2	6.1	5.6	8.0	77.5	84.9
Romania	17.3	17.1	17.7	17.2	18.5	19.9	18.5	19.4	18.9	19.8	10.3	10.0

During the period from 1990 to 2005, electricity generation at nuclear power plants in Ukraine increased from 76.2 to 88.78 billion kWh, while generation at thermal power plants decreased from 201.8 to 73 billion kWh. Thus, during this difficult period for Ukraine, nuclear energy remained the only stable source of electricity. Moreover, nuclear energy occupies one of the leading positions in the Energy Strategy of Ukraine [1,5].

It should be noted that the use of nuclear technologies in the world extends beyond the provision of low-carbon energy. These technologies also help control the spread of diseases, assist doctors in diagnosing and treating patients, provide energy for space exploration missions, and more. Accordingly, this diversity of applications of nuclear energy places

nuclear technologies at the center of global efforts aimed at achieving their sustainable development.

An analysis of statistical data for the period from 1970 to 2022 made it possible to construct the structure of nuclear energy production by continents (Fig. 1 Annual nuclear energy generation in the world from 1970 to 2022 (in GWh) [6]. Nuclear energy generation (GWh): Western and Central Europe, South America, North America, Eastern Europe and Russia, Asia, Africa.

Fig. 1. Annual nuclear energy generation in the world from 1970 to 2022 (in GWh)

The main problems of nuclear energy in Ukraine include the need for continuous improvement of the safety and operational reliability of all control systems and equipment of operating nuclear reactors, as well as solving the problem of handling and storage of spent nuclear fuel (SNF) and radioactive waste (RW). There is also an urgent need to create an optimal infrastructure to ensure the reliable and safe operation and development of nuclear energy in Ukraine.

In the countries of the European Union, the classification of radioactive waste differs. The European Commission has developed recommendations for a classification system for solid RW. However, not all EU member states have implemented it in full.

The main categories of RW include very low-level waste, where the level of radioactivity becomes safe immediately after processing or during temporary storage [7]. Examples of such waste include construction debris, decontaminated metal parts after decommissioning, and uranium-containing

waste. In addition, “intermediate” waste is generated as a result of the operation of nuclear facilities.

There is also low- and intermediate-level waste (LILW). The category of low- and intermediate-level waste is divided into two parts corresponding to the half-lives of radionuclides (approximately 400 Bq/g). There is also long-lived waste, which contains a high concentration of long-lived radionuclides. The most common methods of processing solid radioactive waste (SRW) currently include incineration, cementation, low- and high-pressure compaction, plasma processing, and melting in electric furnaces.

The issue of the strategy for handling spent nuclear fuel from nuclear power plants and high-level radioactive waste remains controversial [8–9]. Many experts believe that spent nuclear fuel should not be considered RW, but rather should be used in the future as an energy resource for other types of reactors that have not yet found commercial application. There are three main criteria outlined in waste management concepts [7]:

- a) whether to dismantle fuel elements or leave them intact;
- b) whether to dispose of them in geological repositories or store them on the surface;
- c) whether to carry out final disposal or temporary storage until new and more effective disposal methods are developed.

Conclusions. Leading positions in the ranking of countries by the sustainability of national energy policy are ensured by the predominance of renewable energy sources in the energy balance structure. Such governments stimulate, at the national level, the development of innovative green technologies to ensure the transition to a carbon-neutral economy, which guarantees the ability of the national economy to provide uninterrupted and equal access to energy resources for all interested parties in sufficient quantities and at competitive prices.

The above makes it possible to conclude that, in order to improve the economic efficiency of Ukrainian nuclear power plants and support their development, further research and development are necessary in such areas as the development and implementation of programs for the management of spent nuclear fuel and radioactive waste, as well as the creation of an optimal infrastructure to ensure the reliable and safe operation and development of nuclear energy in Ukraine.

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